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Scenario Exploration System

Responsible Futuring

Quick Guide

Please note, this document has been written during the development phase of the RRI2Scale SES Version. Thus, the information provided inside of this booklet is provisional and may be subject to change.

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Scenario Exploration System

Smart cities, energy and transport

5-14
participants

1
moderator

3
hours

Introduction to SES

The Scenario Exploration System (SES) is a tool that was developed by the European Commission's Joint Research Centre (JRC), EU Policy Lab, to facilitate the practical use of scenarios from foresight studies. The original motivation behind this development was to create a platform on which EU policymakers and other stakeholders could explore and engage with foresight scenarios in a quick and interactive process that should make it easier to apply foresight to policy making. Running this session enables participants to develop a long-term perspective and consider visions and strategies that include policy makers at different governance levels, business, academia and civil society representatives and the general public.

The usual format of the session that explores two opposing alternative futures takes about 3 hours. Over the past years, the tool has proved to have a broad range of applications that appealed to diverse audiences ranging from EU policymakers, member states, civil society and business representatives, academics and university students. It was run from all around the world. A number of thematic adaptations have been developed inside the JRC as well as by external partner organisations and independent third parties.

The SES is available to any interested party under a Creative Commons licence (CC-BY-SA) that lets users use it and transform it according to their own needs as this project has also done.

The RRI2SCALE edition of the SES emerged from the research done for RRI2SCALE and is based on scenarios that have been researched for RRI2SCALE.* Its objective is to stimulate non-divisive and future-oriented debates to help participants who are making decisions regarding the future of energy, mobility and cities in their regions to appreciate positions of different stakeholders and to align their actions with relative certainties and uncertainties.

Example of a testing session in progress

Description of the session

The Scenario Exploration System (SES) is a tool to enable participants to stimulate their possible paths towards the future in relation to an issue of their choice around an exploration board. It operates as a board game.

The purpose of the Scenario Exploration System is to have participants experience and act through plausible alternative futures, by thinking and conversing outside of their usual frame of reference. The aim is not to play a game and win, but rather to promote a constructive conversation amongst key actors, and to promote integrated long-term thinking in a spirit of collaboration.

*A.Dijkstra,M.Berg et al (2021). Techno-moral scenarios for territorial R&I futures in the domains of intelligent cities, energy and transport. Deliverable 2.2 for the RRI2SCALE project

Scenario Exploration System

Smart cities, energy and transport

Four-five explorers develop and take up roles (see next section) to chart their own courses towards their long-term objectives. They take actions to reach these objectives over three rounds towards a certain time horizon (in the RRI2SCALE version 10 years from the present day). A fifth participant, the Public Voice, analyses the actions taken at every round and gives feedback and value to the actions taken by the characters.

Individual success though is completely subjective as the different participants will likely aim to gain different knowledge from this session. Collective success will be decided at the end of each scenario, when participants are asked to debate about whether or not "we have achieved a sustainable future" (question subject to change). It is worth noting that the SES offers a variety of ways to determine victory: the character wielding the most influence by collecting the highest number of points throughout the three rounds; the character who has reached his/her own long-term objective; or collectively by how close the players' actions have brought them to a sustainable future. Each of which lends themselves to different insights and discussions. For the RRI2SCALE sessions we have chosen one that lends itself to collaboration and collective goals.

In the course of a 3-hour session, participants experience this time journey twice, holding the same roles under contrasting scenarios and pursuing the same long-term visions. The Scenario Exploration System can be applied to various scenarios and used to discuss a range of issues. Roles are flexible.

The standard version described here uses two policymakers, one civil society representative and one business representative.

Scenario Exploration System

Roles

The Public Voice

The public voice represents a substantial group of citizens and voters. They can choose to support or to rebel against the other Scenario Explorers. As the Public Voice is an observer, its influence will not be expressed through actions but through its analysis of the situation and the assessment he/she will write and share with everyone at the end of each round.

The Scenario Explorers

Policymaker

This can be either an EU policy maker or a policymaker at the supranational level. This player should represent a key actor in a public or political administration responsible for decision-making and implementation in the topic being explored.

Business

This should be a business that has a meaningful involvement and/or stake in the topic under discussion. It can be a large or multinational company that has an influential role or a small- to medium-sized business that wields some local influence.

Civil Society Organisation

This should be a civil society organisation that undertake activities that can influence decision making and/or influence public opinion.

Academia

This should be an academic institute that produces research relative to the theme and which can influence decision making and/or influence public opinion. It can be a local university, faculty or laboratory. Alternatively, if an academic organisation exists in the region/country it can be chosen as well.

Scenario Exploration System

Elements overview

The following are the elements that are needed in order to run a SES session:

SES Board

Resource Tokens

Scenario Detail Cards

Scenario detail cards contain a number of events that are happening in each scenario. There are three different scenario detail cards per time horizon, each containing the events belonging to each year.

Scenario Disks

Scenario disks give an overview of the socio-economic situation in each scenario by showing how the resources are distributed amongst all participants/roles.

Megatrend Cards

Megatrend cards present global trends that strongly affect all scenarios and must be taken into account by participants while decision-making.

Action Cards

Action cards are role specific. Each explorer (except the public voice) will receive a set of action cards with example actions that they can take. Participants are also allowed and encouraged to come up with their own action cards.

Scenario Exploration System

Elements overview

What If Cards

These are variable drivers that have been identified as potentially relevant but with a high level of uncertainty (in terms of the direction they will take).

They influence gameplay in a random fashion, by becoming concerns of varying importance for the participants and the Public Voice. The use of "What If" cards is completely optional, and it can be a great resource to unstick the session when needed.

Scenario Exploration System

Setting up the session

To execute a successful SES session a few preparations are necessary. Namely **space**, **materials** and **time**. Depending on the type of session, the space and materials can vary from physical, digital or a hybrid between these two. Lastly, it is also crucial to allocate enough time to this session in order to achieve the best results and experience.

Space

Physical Session

The SES can be run physically, digitally or in a hybrid way. For a physical session, physical space is needed, preferably around a **table large enough to fit an A0 paper and give space for the participants' cards as well**. A simple, private and welcoming environment is important for the participants to feel comfortable.

If the plan is to run parallel sessions, it is **important to book a room large enough to provide enough privacy and space for all participants and sessions**. An alternative would be to use different rooms for the different sessions, however, this is not desired since it would difficult the task of assisting the Session Masters when needed.

Digital Session

To run a digital session, there are **two key choices**: the **communication platform** and the **environment platform**. For example, Zoom or Microsoft Teams can be used for the communication amongst all participants and **Miro or Mural** can be used as the environment where the session elements will be held.

Hybrid Session

During a hybrid session, the participants will join in both physically and digitally. To run the session, the **same requirements as the digital session are needed**: a communication channel and a collaboration platform where the environment can be held.

Additionally, a **physical space will be needed to host physical participants**. This space must be equipped with a **good camera** and a **single conference microphone** so that proper communication and interaction can be established between all the participants.

Lastly, if necessary, an extra moderator could be present during the session to ensure that all participants have a good experience.

Materials

Physical Session

For physical sessions, **all the SES elements must be printed** - i.e.: the SES board (printed in an A0 if possible), and all the cards and tokens shown in the "Elements Overview" section of this guide. Furthermore, **a few pens** (at least one per participant) and **post-it notes** will be needed.

In addition, it is also important to **make sure that all the participants feel comfortable** throughout the entire session. Thus, the availability of water, tea/coffee and snacks is highly advised.

Scenario Exploration System

Setting up the session

Digital Session

For digital sessions, all the **SES elements need to be imported** into the platform where the session environment will be hosted (e.g.: Miro or Mural). Alternatively, the organisers may choose to create their own set of cards by using the tools available in given platform. **The latter option is highly unadvised.** Furthermore, if the budget allows, mailing a welcome package including drinks and/or snacks would be great.

Hybrid Session

Hybrid sessions need the **same materials and set-up as online sessions**. Participants that are physically present are recommended to bring their own digital devices (i.e.: laptops and high-end tablets, **NOT SMARTPHONES**) through which they can access the SES platform (Miro or Mural).

Time

Finally in regards to time, a single SES session takes a **minimum of 3 hours to complete** (including explorer creation, exploring both scenarios, and discussion). Allowing **time for reflection and discussion is vital** for getting the most out of the session. Therefore, make sure to **allocate a bit more than 3 hours!**

Scenario Exploration System

Example round

STEP 1: Preparing the exploration

At the beginning of the Exploration Session, the participants are asked to develop their role and define their long term objectives in detail.

For example, the business actor should have a clear business plan, define its location, size, market, suppliers, etc. The civil society organisation should define its scope, objective, membership, etc. Policymakers should describe how they hope their policy area will develop in the next 10 years.

In the meanwhile, the Session Master sets up the board with the required elements (see [Page 5](#)).

- The selected **Scenario Disc** is put in the middle of the board.
- The **Resource Tokens** are distributed to the Public Voice and the Scenario Explorer according to the amount indicated on the Scenario disc.
- The **Action Cards** are given to each Scenario Explorer together with two **Real-Life cards**
- etc.

STEP 2: Exploring the scenario

First Round | First Time Horizon (2021)

We are now on the first time horizon. The Scenario Exploration Master tells a story based on the first **Scenario Detail card**. The Scenario Exploration Master then lays down the pile of **"What if"** cards face down and reveals the first one. This first "What if" card will influence the first round of the scenario exploration as the Scenario Explorers should take this factor into account while planning their actions.

Scenario Explorers decide on an **Action card** and place it on the **board** - in the zone corresponding to the time horizon. They support their action with own resources of their choice by putting **resource tokens** on the **action card**. During the round, each Scenario Explorer can use one **Real-life card** according to the instructions that each carries. The explorers that have used a Real-life card pick a new one from the pile.

Once all four Scenario Explorers have taken action, the Public Voice reacts by attributing its special **red resource tokens**.

At the end of the round, the Scenario Exploration Master creates a wrap-up story of the round and collects the scores.*

***Scores:** The scores are the multiplication of the resources allocated to each action by the number of red tokens attributed to the corresponding actions by the Public Voice.

Scenario Exploration System

Example round

Second Round | Second Time Horizon (2026)

The Scenario Exploration Master continues the story based on the next Scenario Detail card (next time horizon) and optionally reveals the next "What if" card.

Similarly to the first round, the Scenario Explorers put one **Action card** on the board and support it with **resource tokens** of their choice.

What is different now is that in the 1st round, the explorers act individually. In the 2nd and 3rd rounds they can, in addition to acting individually, also collaborate upon request with one, two, or three other explorers.

The Explorers can solicit collaboration from other players when they are explaining their individual actions. Other players can reflect on this and decide to collaborate only after all players have finished putting down their actions. If a collaboration is agreed, the Scenario Explorer who wants to engage in a collaboration puts some of his/her own **resource tokens** on the action(s) he/she wants to collaborate with.

If collaborations happen, the original owner of the action card receives the score for the sum of his/her resource tokens plus those of the collaborating partner, multiplied by the red tokens allocated by the Public Voice (if given any). The collaborating partner also receives points from that action: but only the points that equal the resource tokens that he/she invested in the collaboration multiplied by the red tokens attributed by the Public Voice.

Again, once all four Scenario Explorers have taken action (and collaborated), the Public Voice reacts by attributing its special **red resource tokens**.

At the end of the round the Scenario Exploration Master creates a wrap up story of the round and collects the scores.

Third Round | Third Time Horizon (2031)

The third round is identical to the second round.

STEP 3: Discussion

At the end, the Scenario Exploration Master summarises the scenario exploration, calculates the overall final scores on the scoring sheet and asks the Scenario Explorers to assess how well they have managed to reach their long-term objectives.

